

Formulation of Open-Source Hybrid Two-Step Neutronics Toolchains for Space Microreactors Characterization

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ABSTRACT

The renewed global interest in nuclear microreactors for space missions has opened a new research area focused on the simulation of these compact reactor concepts. Among them, the heat-pipe microreactor stands out as the leading candidate due to its autonomy and compactness. This work presents recent efforts aimed at fully predicting the neutronic behavior of such reactors. Given the interest of several European organizations in a future where the simulation tools used by researchers and designers are not subject to export controls, the main constraint of this analysis is the exclusive use of open-source software and its further development for heat-pipe-cooled microreactors.

This study demonstrates the feasibility of employing currently available open-source tools within a hybrid two-step neutronic workflow for characterizing a simplified version of the KRUSTY microreactor in a steady-state scenario. Both diffusion and discrete ordinates methods were assessed, and the limitations the former has for reactors of this scale were identified. A fine energy group structure was proven to be necessary, together with an adequate way of representing the anisotropy of the model and a fine mesh for the representation of the accumulated power deposition towards the borders of the core.

Keywords: Nuclear Electric Propulsion, Microreactor, OpenMC, open-source, OpenFoam

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent efforts to advance the technological maturity of nuclear reactors for space applications are underway in several laboratories worldwide. This interest is supported by various space agencies seeking more cost-effective and sustainable methods for deep-space exploration. Two main technological approaches are currently under consideration: Nuclear Electric Propulsion (NEP) and Nuclear Thermal Propulsion (NTP). NEP systems generate electricity by converting the heat produced in a power reactor, which is then supplied to an array of ion thrusters that propel the spacecraft. Among the different reactor designs under development for this approach, heat-pipe-cooled microreactors, operating passively without the need for the assistance of gravity, have emerged as a leading candidate. However, their underlying physics remain an active research topic. In particular, the neutronic behaviour of the core is markedly influenced by its small size and strong heterogeneity, which lead to significant neutron leakage and pronounced anisotropic effects resulting from the use of light materials as reflectors.

In this paper, the neutronic modelling and characterization of a specific heat-pipe-cooled microreactor design is presented. A key constraint of the analysis is the exclusive use of open-source, non-export-controlled tools throughout the entire neutronic calculation chain. This approach reflects one of the central objectives of the broader MARVIS-OpenSPACE project which aims, in long term, to establish a fully open-source platform for the simulation and assessment of heat-pipe-cooled microreactors for space applications. Within this framework, neutronic analysis constitutes a fundamental component of the research effort.

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2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Calculation Workflow and Codes

The aim of this analysis is to demonstrate the applicability of existing neutronic codes to the modelling of heat-pipe-cooled microreactors. The overall workflow follows a hybrid two-step approach. First, a Monte Carlo tool is used to define the reference solution and generate the homogenized Multi Group Cross Section (MGXS) library. Then, a deterministic code, employing diffusion or transport methods (or both), is applied to compute the main reactor parameters. For the stochastic stage, OpenMC [1] was selected to provide both the reference model and the MGXS library for the subsequent deterministic step. Although OpenMC is not the only available non-export-controlled Monte Carlo code, it is the most actively maintained and well documented, with a large user community. Its capabilities for group constants generation also facilitate the post-processing of tallies required for library construction.

For the deterministic stage, several open-source codes were reviewed and assessed. The evaluation considered numerical methods, discretization schemes, acceleration techniques, and the availability of transient capabilities. Coarse-mesh nodal and finite difference codes, commonly used in Light Water Reactor analysis, were excluded due to their limited suitability for the use of unstructured meshes usually needed for the highly heterogeneous geometry and the strong spatial effects that are characteristics of microreactor cores. Instead, Finite Element (FEM) and Finite Volume (FVM) based solvers were prioritized. The final set of candidate codes considered in this work is:

- GeN-Foam (24.06) [2]: an OpenFoam-based multiphysics code that integrates neutronics, thermohydraulics, and thermomechanics solvers. For neutronics, it includes steady-state and transient diffusion, steady-state discrete ordinates (S_N), and both steady-state and transient Simplified Spherical Harmonics of order 3 (SP_3) methods. Its main advantages are the built-in multiphysics coupling and the availability of acceleration schemes.
- FEMFFUSION (1.0) [3]: a FEM-based code built on the deal.II library. It can solve the diffusion and the Simplified Spherical Harmonics (SP_N) equations in both steady-state and transients. It employs a continuous Galerkin discretization scheme and supports the use of high-order elements.
- OpenSN (0.0.1) [4]: a FEM-based code written in C++ that implements the S_N method for steady-state scenarios. It uses a discontinuous Galerkin discretization with Piece-Wise Linear polynomial, supports quadratures with high angular resolution and incorporates specific acceleration techniques for S_N solvers, such as synthetic diffusion and the second-moment method [5].
- FEMcore (0.4.30) [6]: an in-house finite element-based code written in Fortran. It solves the diffusion equation in both steady-state and transient scenarios, using a Galerkin discretization with B-spline polynomials. Chebyshev polynomials are used and Anderson acceleration technique is implemented for the power iterations.

2.2. KRUSTY-like Model

For the initial assessment of the selected codes and calculation process, a simplified model of the Kilopower Reactor Using Stirling Technology (KRUSTY) reactor was adopted. The KRUSTY core consists of a high-enriched UMo monolith, surrounded by eight sodium heat pipes that transfer heat from the core to the power conversion system. The feasibility of this system was demonstrated through a prototype that was built and successfully tested under transient conditions [7]. The reactor provides an output of 5 kWth and 1 kWe, and was developed by the DOE and NASA with the objective of serving as a potential power source for future lunar surface missions. Figure 1 shows the cross section of the original prototype as well as the simplified model employed in this work. The simplifications were taken from the analysis of Sun et al. [8], and retains the core and the most relevant surrounding regions for the neutronic analysis. Due to the small dimensions of the core and the high neutron leakage, the shielding could also have a relatively high importance on the neutronics [9]. However, for this first assessment, the simplified model was considered sufficient. Although the original simplified model is 3D, a further

simplified 2D version was used for this preliminary assessment to help distinguish biases arising from the model itself from those introduced by the chosen tools and their implementation.

Figure 1. KRUSTY model.

For the generation of MGXS, an initial iterative analysis was carried out to determine both the optimal number and distribution of energy groups. Since this reactor has a small geometry and because of the presence of the beryllium oxide reflector, it was found crucial to account for the scattering anisotropy. For this reason, to generate multi group libraries, three different representations were chosen:

- Isotropic (Non-corrected): A MGXS library with the non-corrected kernel.
- Isotropic (P1-corrected): A MGXS library with isotropic scattering kernel that was corrected using the P1 method to incorporate the anisotropic effects into one scattering matrix, suitable to correct the isotropic representation for the diffusion simulations.
- Anisotropic (P3): A MGXS library with anisotropic scattering kernel with a Legendre moment up to 3.

Both diffusion and discrete ordinates methods were used, according to the availability of each code. In the case of the GeN-Foam calculations, the application of discontinuity factors [2] was also evaluated. This equivalence technique consists in the definition of a scalar that is applied in the interface of two homogenized regions and that allows a discontinuity in the flux between materials.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Monte Carlo

The simulations in OpenMC were run with 350 total batches, 300 active batches and 200 000 particles per batch. These parameters were chosen after evaluating the convergence of the source as well as the k -effective and integral fluxes and reaction rates over the homogenized regions. The reference solution generated by OpenMC reported a k -effective of 1.18943 ± 0.00012 . Following the procedure stated in the previous section, the reference solution and the MGXS library was generated and an analysis on the impact of the MGXS structure was performed.

An evaluation on the quality of the energy group structures was done holding Monte Carlo multi-group simulations within OpenMC, using the MGXS libraries generated within the same code. This procedure can give idea of how well the structure is representing the overall neutronic balance. Table I contains a summary of the k -effective results obtained for the MGXS library analysis. From these results, it can be seen the importance of the correction in the scattering representation and the use of a suitable group structure that enables the correct representation of the spectral phenomena of this core. A 30 energy

Table I. OpenMC Multi Group simulations for different scattering representations and group structures.

MG Structure	Isotropic ($\Delta\rho_{ref}$)	Isotropic P1-corrected ($\Delta\rho_{ref}$)	Anisotropic P3 ($\Delta\rho_{ref}$)
2 groups	1.39207 ± 0.00010 (12238)	1.35127 ± 0.00010 (10069)	1.34944 ± 0.00010 (9969)
9 groups	1.29636 ± 0.00010 (6935)	1.22438 ± 0.00010 (2400)	1.23103 ± 0.00010 (2841)
22 groups	1.27247 ± 0.00010 (5487)	1.18944 ± 0.00010 (1)	1.19725 ± 0.00010 (549)
30 groups	1.26286 ± 0.00010 (4889)	1.18099 ± 0.00010 (-601)	1.18964 ± 0.00010 (15)

Figure 2. Integrated radial fission rate distribution along the core for the continuous MC simulation (reference) and the multi-group MC simulations, using different scattering representations.

group structure was found suitable when using a P3 representation, however, it is worth to notice that, when using the P1-corrected isotropic kernel, the 30 group structure overestimates the leakage. The tendency on the results is also supported by comparing the distribution of the fission rate generated by the different group structures when running each case in OpenMC Multi Group calculation mode. In Figure 2, it can be seen that a coarse group structure results in the overestimation of the fission rate in almost all the radius of the core, with the exception of the region closer to the outer boundary, where the accumulated fission rate is lower than the reference. However, with 30 energy groups, both the MGXS libraries with isotropic corrected and anisotropic scattering cross sections provide a better match to the fission rate distribution.

3.2. Deterministic Simulations

3.2.1. Convergence and Performance

As the second stage of the analysis, the open-source deterministic codes previously described were tested using the same model. For each code, a mesh convergence study was carried out. The convergence was evaluated as the difference between the k -effective of each simulation and the corresponding value of the case with the finest mesh considered for each code and method. It is worth to notice that this convergence analysis was not computed to get the theoretical mesh convergence. Instead, the study was focused on the dependence of the k -effective on the mesh refinement for the areas of greater importance in the model, the active core and its immediate boundaries. However, the results showed that, for GeN-Foam to converge, a finer mesh resolution than that used for the other codes was required in the non-multiplying regions to achieve convergence to the reference values, reported in the next section.

Figure 3 presents the convergence of the k -effective for the calculations of the different codes. The error is plotted against the number of unknowns, or degrees of freedom (DOFs), of each simulation. This metric comes naturally for FEM-based codes, as it accounts for the number of mesh nodes, the number

Figure 3. Relative error of the k -effective (with reference to the finer mesh size for each case) as a function of the degrees of freedom (or number of unknowns) of the simulation.

Figure 4. Execution time of the simulations as a function of the number of cells of the mesh.

of energy groups and the amount of coefficients of the selected polynomial. For GeN-Foam, the DOFs can be defined in a less conventional and approximated way as the number of mesh cells multiplied by the number of energy groups (and quadrature points for the S_N calculations). The results show that, even though the convergence rate is similar, GeN-Foam in general needs a higher resolution than FEM-based codes with linear elements to achieve the similar errors for the diffusion cases. The application of the discontinuity factors [2] for this code leads to less variation in the reactivity across different meshes, as a result of the fixation of the flux gradients in the borders of the regions. On the other hand, FEMFUSION and FEMcore display roughly similar performance when the number of DOFs is considered and across the different polynomial degrees used, although FEMcore starts from a higher relative error for coarser meshes. The improvement on the convergence rate when using a discontinuous FEM-based code, that allows for a strictest prediction of local reaction rates, can be exemplified when looking at the variations on the k -effective for OpenSN, which are very small in comparison with the curves obtained

for GeN-Foam S_N .

Regarding the performance evaluation of the selected codes, the execution time required for each simulation is reported for all the cases considered in Figure 4, this time against the number of cells of the mesh considered. All diffusion simulations were executed with 1 processor, while the S_N simulations were run with 28 processors. In terms of computational performance for the diffusion cases, FEMcore stands up as the most efficient for linear elements. Regarding the transport calculations, OpenSN exhibits superior efficiency compared to GeN-Foam, behaviour that becomes less prominent when increasing the number of cells in the mesh. The use of a higher Legendre order increments the execution time for both codes.

3.3. Steady-State Results

Once an optimal mesh was determined for each code, the set of deterministic calculations was conducted for the converged discretizations. Both diffusion and transport results can be seen in table II. Regarding the diffusion results, for all simulations without discontinuity factors, the predicted k-effective is inaccurate with a strong underestimation on the reactivity. In contrast, the use of discontinuity factors in GeN-Foam leads to an improved yet high positive error on the k-effective. The discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that the adjustable discontinuity factors in GeN-Foam is limited to isotropic values to all boundaries of one region. This could lead to an inaccurate estimation of the internal local currents and an underestimation of the total leakage. Looking at the results for the transport method considered, discrete ordinates, a key factor affecting the accuracy was found to be the representation of the anisotropy: in the cases where non-corrected isotropic scattering was used, the k-effective was overestimated by approximately 5000 pcm. However, the use of the corrected isotropic and the anisotropic MGXS libraries significantly improve the prediction of the reactivity.

Table II. Deterministic results for the converged meshes of each code, using an energy structure of 30 groups. Linear elements were used for all FEM-based simulations. All S_N simulations were run with the same Gauss-Legendre-Chebyshev quadrature ($S(12, 6)$).

Code	Legendre Order	K-effective	$\Delta\rho$ MC [pcm]	Peaking Factor	Power RMS [%]
OpenMC (ref)	-	1.18943 (12)	-	3.78	-
FEMFFUSION		1.12102	-5121	3.17	3.73
FEMcore	P0	1.12102	-5121	3.14	3.95
GeN-Foam w/o disc. Factors	(P1-corr.)	1.12586	-4747	2.71	4.86
GeN-Foam w. disc. Factors		1.20918	1373	2.32	3.71
OpenSN	P0	1.26709	5153	3.14	1.66
	P0 (P1-corr.)	1.18353	-418	3.13	1.52
	P3	1.18943	0	3.15	1.46
GeN-Foam (S_N)	P0	1.26602	5086	2.31	3.84
	P0 (P1-corr.)	1.18824	-84	2.32	3.59
	P3	1.18946	2	2.33	3.58

On the other hand, the reported peaking factor was computed using a volume-weighted sum of the local power over the radial section of the model. The maximum always occurs at the outer edge, and none of the codes fully capture the steep accumulation. Regarding the power root mean square factor, the S_N results depend on the level of anisotropic representation, while for diffusion the use of discontinuity factors reduces the discrepancy. Nevertheless, the FVM-based code still exhibits significantly larger errors for both uncorrected diffusion and the S_N method. Apart from what is reported in the table, an analysis on the choice of quadrature showed that this parameter had minimal impact on the results, which can be attributed to the simplicity of the 2D model.

Regarding the power distribution results, Figure 5 compares the integrated power along the core radius. It is important to note that, in order to achieve the convergence, the mesh generated for each code had to be refined near the outer wall of the core, since the concentration of power around the interfaces between the core, the heat pipes, and the vacuum chamber produces sharp gradients that deterministic methods cannot fully capture. Consequently, even in the converged meshes, the maximum error in the power distribution is concentrated in that region for all simulations. It is also worth noting that the diffusion cases exhibit a lower maximum error (from 7.5 to 10%) compared to the GeN-Foam S_N calculations (around 12.5%). Among the tested codes, OpenSN demonstrates a better ability to capture this behavior, showing as higher error approximately 5% for the isotropic case, which decreases to about 2.5% for the corrected and anisotropic cases. In the diffusion case, the use of discontinuity factors in GeN-Foam lowers the maximum power accumulation observed in the aforementioned region but improves the overall accuracy along the volume of the core.

Figure 5. Comparison of integrated power distributions and their relative errors. All simulations were performed using 30 energy groups.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of open-source neutronic tools for microreactor simulations revealed key strengths and limitations. A hybrid approach, combining Monte Carlo-generated cross sections with diffusion and transport solvers, proved effective, using both Finite Element and Finite Volume discretizations. For the benchmarking of the a KRUSTY-like model, featuring a fast microreactor with a monolithic high-enriched uranium core, a fine energy group structure (30 groups) together with a transport method and a consistent treatment of scattering anisotropy was required to accurately predict the reactivity. In terms of power distribution, the results showed that a highly refined mesh was necessary in regions with sharp gradients.

Since FEM-based codes demonstrated better performance than FVM-based codes and greater capability for accurately representing reactor parameters with higher order elements, future work will focus on applying diffusion corrections to FEM-based diffusion solvers. In addition, efforts will be directed

toward improving input data management, implementing feedback mechanisms, and developing transient models to complete the neutronic characterization of heat-pipe microreactors.

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